

FORMS OF CONTROL AND ASSESSMENT OF THE ACTIVITY OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *At present, the pedagogy of preschool education is faced with the tasks of monitoring, controlling and analyzing the educational process, identifying specific goals and the significance of assessment, and improving them. When solving these problems, the use of modern methods of analyzing the educational process and their further improvement is determined. According to the theory of the researcher, modern requirements for control and monitoring are identified.*

Keywords: *educational process, control, analysis, observation, modern methods, improvement.*

Introduction. The economic power of each country is determined by the improvement of the level of social and spiritual life, the competitiveness of the educational system, and the development of science in it.

Today, our state sets a number of tasks for the preschool education system, like all types of education. These tasks consist of requirements such as creation of conditions for comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children in the preschool education system, taking into account advanced foreign experiences, increasing the quality of preschool education, fundamental improvement of the quality of preparing children for school in preschool education organizations, introducing modern education programs and technologies widely used in world practice to the educational and upbringing process, as well as, the improvement of the mechanism of training and professional development of pedagogic personnel for preschool education organizations.

Research object and used methods

As the object of the study, the resources on the control of the preschool education system, mainly the process of implementation of the control of education, have been taken. The methods of classification, complex study and analysis have been used to cover the research topic.

The obtained results and their analysis

Assessment of the activities of educational organizations is the main form of state control. In our republic, the content, level and quality of personnel training in educational organizations is carried out through assessment and control of compliance with state educational standards, state educational requirements and educational programs. The pre-school education system requires constant control over the proper and high-quality organization of the educational process.

The methods of analyzing and controlling the educational process in pedagogical activity have been noticed by a number of pedagogic scientists, and a number of reasons and methods of analyzing the educational process have been studied and substantiated by them.

Information about this are reflected in R.M.Sarsenbaeva's articles on lesson analysis, D.Samadova's scientific research entitled "Lesson analysis and its scientific didactic foundations" and P.Yusupova, F.R.Kadirova's teaching manuals, I.V. Grosheva's methodological manual "Observation and evaluation".

In foreign countries it has been covered through the articles and methodological recommendations of A.I. Vasileva, A.P. Myakinchenko, L.N. Levashova, I.V. Nikishina.

Implementation of control over the activities of educational organizations and controlling, monitoring and analysis of educational and upbringing work are carried out by authorized bodies and responsible persons. Its basis is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Upbringing" and the Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Approval of the State Standard of Preschool Education and Upbringing". The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" stipulates that state control in the field of education is carried out in order to determine the content and quality of education provided in the educational system in accordance with state educational standards, state educational requirements and curricula, as well as legal requirements.

The principles of our state in the field of education are as follows:

- recognition of the priority of education;
- freedom to choose the form of education;
- non-discrimination in education;
- provision of equal opportunities for education;
- inculcation of national and universal human values in education and upbringing;
- humanitarian, democratic nature of education and upbringing;
- continuity and consistency of education;
- compulsory eleven-year education and one year of preparation of children between the ages of six and seven for general secondary education;
- access to education for all within the framework of state educational standards and state educational requirements;
- the uniformity and differentiation of the approach to the selection of educational programs;
- education throughout a person's life;
- guaranteed social protection of pedagogues in society;
- secular nature of the educational system;
- promotion of knowledge, ability and talent;
- the harmony of state and public administration in the educational system;
- openness and transparency in the field of educational activities [1].

Activities in the field of education in our republic are carried out based on these principles within the framework of the law. In the implementation of control over the quality of education conducted in educational organizations, the principles established by the law are followed, as well as control principles such as independence, impartiality, openness, transparency, fairness, periodicity during the implementation of control [4].

In the control of educational organizations, including in the implementation of control over the quality of education in preschool educational organizations, the Educational Inspectorate, competent state administration bodies in the field of education assist [3].

In cases where the content and quality of education provided by educational organizations is found to be inconsistent with the laws on education or the lack of sufficient competences of learners, the Education Inspectorate has the right to submit a report to them to eliminate the inconsistency. In the event that the identified inconsistency is not eliminated, the Education Inspectorate has the right to cancel the state accreditation certificate of the educational organization

in accordance with the law. Such control is carried out on the basis of procedures established by law. [2].

It is not allowed to check the quality of education of educational organizations, the organization of the educational process, the work of pedagogues, the mastery of students, and the implementation of other controls by bodies that do not have the authority to control the quality of education. Such controls are called external controls.

According to the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the approval of the state standard of preschool education and upbringing", the purpose of the control over compliance with the requirements of the State Standard established for preschool education is to determine the level of fulfillment of the requirements established in the state standard, and to assure education and upbringing quality based on the implementation of necessary measures [3].

Control over compliance with the requirements of the state standard in preschool educational organizations is carried out by the relevant Ministry of Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regional divisions as follows:

implementation of state requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age;

state of implementation of the state curriculum of preschool education and upbringing;

compliance with hygienic requirements for the organization of full and safe feeding in state pre-school educational organizations;

compliance with departmental construction standards in the construction of state preschool educational organizations;

equipping state pre-school educational organizations with game sets, toys, furniture, equipment and other technical means;

compliance with fire safety requirements in state pre-school educational organizations are monitored [6].

In accordance with the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 802 dated December 22, 2020 "On approval of the state standard of preschool education and upbringing", control over the quality of education in state preschool education organizations is carried out through four types of controls.

The first type of control is internal control. Internal control is carried out by the head of the state preschool education organization and the district (city) departments and regional and Tashkent city education departments, which are high-ranking in the management of preschool education.

The second type of control is external control - it is carried out by state bodies and organizations that have the authority to check the activities of state pre-school education organizations established by legislation.

The third type of control is public control - it is carried out according to the established procedure by the public commission organized in makhalla and village assemblies.

The fourth type of control is assessment at the national and international level - it is carried out in cooperation with preschool education management bodies, other organizations, including international organizations, based on the relevant decision of the government and the requirements of international agreements [3].

According to the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the procedure for certification and state accreditation of state educational institutions and non-state educational organizations", inspections are carried out for the purpose of certification and state accreditation of educational institutions, including preschool educational organizations. In accordance with this resolution, internal and external assessments aimed at increasing the accountability of educational organizations for the quality of education and determining the quality of education in each educational organization are conducted. Internal evaluation is considered self-evaluation and is a process of self-evaluation of educational activities by educational organizations based on accreditation indicators and criteria. Based on its result, an internal evaluation report of the educational organization is drawn up. The main purpose of internal evaluation is to prepare the organization for external evaluation. In the process of internal evaluation, the organization's activity is evaluated based on certification indicators and criteria, and the compliance of the quality and content of education with state requirements is studied based on 4 directions, 7 fields, 19 standards and 62 indicators [6]. Actions are taken to eliminate identified existing problems and deficiencies, and a road map for eliminating deficiencies is drawn up for the organization. The deadlines for eliminating the shortcomings identified in the road map and the persons responsible for it are determined and eliminated. According to the resolution, the process of internal evaluation of activities of preschool educational organizations is carried out by the internal evaluation commission established by the order of the head of the organization based on the decision of the pedagogical council of the organization. Based on the decision of the Pedagogical Council, the composition of the internal evaluation commission is formed in the composition of not less than 9 people. The commission may involve a methodologist, head of the economy, chairman of the trade union, psychologist, experienced pedagogical staff, members of the Supervisory Board of the organization, representative of the community assembly, and experienced pedagogical staff from other pre-school education organizations. The head of the organization acts as the chairman of the commission. In the process of internal evaluation of the organization, the activity of the educational organization in the last two years is widely and comprehensively analyzed and studied based on the following areas:

- organization of educational process in accordance with state requirements;
- level of development of students;
- implementation of training programs for the next stage of education;
- potential of the leader and educator-pedagogue personnel;
- the state of the material and technical base and the conditions created for the development of pupils;
- compliance with sanitary rules, standards and hygiene regulations, aesthetic requirements and quality of feeding.

In the process of internal evaluation by the control group, the processes of educational activity conducted by all pedagogues working in the educational organization with the trainees are analyzed. The level of development of at least 50% of the trainees in the training group of the organization is studied, and their compatibility with the results on the observation map is compared. At least 50% of the parents of children attending the educational organization receive questionnaires. Also, social questionnaires are conducted with all pedagogues of the educational organization. The results of these questionnaires are also evaluated and taken into account in the evaluation of the quality of the organization.

Observers study the program of the preschool education organization, the planning process of educators-pedagogues, the reflection and appropriateness of annual, monthly, and weekly plans in the execution of plans, creative adaptation of the program by educators and integration assurance. In addition, the organization checks whether the documents required to be maintained by educators are regularly maintained on the basis of current documents, it is determined whether the training topics are developed in accordance with the topics of the month and week and are written according to the plans. The activities of educators-pedagogues who conduct training with children covering all areas of child development are also examined by observers. Educators with experience and professional skills should apply elements of cognitive, physical, social and emotional development of the child when working with children. Children are required not to sit around the table constantly during the training, but to be active during the learning activity.

Preschool education organizations ensure comprehensive development of children. Development support is the process of planning goals and expected results. As a result of acquiring the knowledge and skills specified in the educational program, children acquire the basic competencies defined in the state requirements. Preschool education organizations provide education based on a program that fully meets state requirements. 5 main directions of children's development - physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle, social and emotional development, development of speech, communication, reading and writing skills, creative development areas have been adopted, and the educational program and educational activities planned and implemented based on it requires all areas to be carried out in an integrated manner.

Educators should pay special attention to the formation of national-cultural and historical values during educational activities and inculcate the spirit of patriotism in children. The topics of such classes or the purpose of other thematic activities are required to be recorded in the educator's working register [8].

During the internal control, in addition to the organization of the educational process in accordance with the state requirements, the level of development of the trainees, the implementation of the training program for the next stage of education, the potential of the leader and educator, the state of the material and technical base and the conditions created for the development of the trainees, the sanitary rules, norms and compliance with hygiene standards, aesthetic requirements and quality of food, cooperation with the public and parents are studied and evaluated.

Internal control of preschool education is carried out by the head of the state preschool education organization and district (city) preschool education departments, as well as the department of education of the regions, the head of the preschool education management.

It is known that the internal control and analysis of the educational process in the preschool education system is one of the main forms of leadership of the pedagogical team work of the director and methodologist of the preschool education organization [7]. The main goal of monitoring and analyzing the educational process is to improve pedagogues' teaching methodology by studying whether the educational process conducted by them is properly planned, rationally organized, to eliminate identified deficiencies in this process in a timely manner, and to provide necessary methodological recommendations to pedagogues. In this case, the main goal of conducting control and analysis should not be to find shortcomings, but to provide timely methodical support to pedagogues and study and popularize best practices in their work activities. Control of the educational process in pre-school educational organizations is carried out by

representatives of the organization that monitors the quality of education. This is defined by law. The analysis of the educational process means the study of pedagogical activity and the organization of the process, the organization of practical didactic support based on deep knowledge of its positive and negative aspects.

The essence of pedagogical control is that the heads of the educational organization or the methodologists of the monitoring and work control department of preschool education departments comprehensively study the educational process according to the pre-planned goal. In the implementation of control, a non-specialist should not be allowed to carry out observation and analysis. Properly organized control helps to identify the best creative experiences of pedagogues and generalize and popularize their pedagogical skills [10].

Educational activities are organized by the heads of pre-school educational organizations based on the annual plan. The following goals are considered when analysis is carried out by the head of the organization:

- compliance of the content of educational activities with state requirements and the curriculum;
- availability of training material plan;
- adherence to the main principles of didactics and the principles of preschool education pedagogy in the educational process;
- respective selection of the type, educational methods, means and forms according to the didactic purpose of the educational activity;
- correctly setting the goals of educational activity (educational, upbringing, developmental);
- readiness of the teacher to organize the training;
- the creation of conditions for the formation of child basic competences and the competences in areas of development;
- proper organization and assessment of educational activities.

Conclusion

Observations show that the demands placed on persons responsible for monitoring and analyzing educational processes and control in the pre-school education system are less studied than in school education. Therefore, the pre-school education system, like school education, requires regulation and normalization. Setting such requirements is developed in order to protect field pedagogues, to prevent the occurrence of conflicting situations in the process of activity, to protect against subjective assessment of the work of pedagogues, to prevent violation of pedagogical ethics in the educational process. Organization of control by responsible persons always requires planned implementation. It should be organized in such a way that it awakens in pedagogues a sense of positive initiative, responsibility for their work, positive attitude towards trainees and responsibility for the educational process. Only then will we ensure quality control of the educational process.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг “Таълим тўғрисида”ги Қонуни ЎРҚ -637.-Т.: 2020 й
2. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг “Мақтабгача таълим ва тарбия тўғрисида”ги Қонуни ЎРҚ-595.-Т.: 2019 й
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг “Мақтабгача таълим ва

- тарбиянинг давлат стандартларини тасдиқлаш тўғрисида”ги 802- сон қарори.-Т.: 2019 й
4. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг “Давлат таълим муассасалари ҳамда нодавлат таълим ташкилотларини аттестациядан ва давлат аккредитациядан ўтказиш тартибини такомиллаштириш тўғрисида”ги 470- сон қарори.-Т.: 2019 й
 5. Грошева И.В. Кузатиш ва баҳолаш. Методик қўлланма.-Т.,2020 19 б
 6. Одилов А.А.Мақтабгача таълим ташкилотларини аккредитациядан ўтказиш бўйича услубий қўлланма.-Т.,2020.- 17 б.
 7. Қодирова Ф.Р.Мақтабгача педагогика. -Т.:”Тафаккур”.2019.-562 б.
 8. Содиқова Ш.Мақтабгача педагогика.-Т.:”Tafakkur bo‘stoni”.2013.-247 б.
 9. Сарсенбаева Р.М. Ўқув машғулотларини таҳлил қилиш методикаси.Узлуксиз таълим журнали.Т.: 2016.-№6
 10. Файзиева М.М. Мақтабгача таълим ташкилотларида таълим-тарбия жараёнини назорат қилиш техникаси. Falsafa.2022.195 б